

POSSIBILITIES OF APPLYING GREAT BRITAIN'S EXPERIENCE IN DEVELOPING THE CREATIVE ECONOMY IN UZBEKISTAN

Daminova Madinakhan Bahromjon kizi

teacher of the Department of Systematic Analysis and Mathematical
Modeling of the University of World Economy and Diplomacy

Email: daminovamadina1992@gmail.com

Telephone: +99899960335

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ABSTRACT

Along with digitalization of the world economy, the term creative economy, which includes areas requiring creativity, has begun to gain its importance. Great Britain, which began to pay special attention to this concept, popularized its experience at such a speed that now it has many segments on 3 continents. The Creative Central Asia Network, organized by the British Council, acted as an accelerator in the wide spread of this approach in Central Asian countries. In the article, it is planned to study the British experience of this approach and make suggestions to Uzbekistan.

Introduction

Recently, the phenomenon of creative (creative) spheres has been of great interest to researchers, because it is one of the most dynamic and at the same time uncertainly developing directions not only of the modern socio-cultural space, but also of entrepreneurship. Not surprisingly, the term "creative industries" includes a number of meanings, from economic to socio-cultural.

Creative economy is a broader term and should be understood as a new type of economy. Also, the production process is not based on traditional types of resources, and the increase in the value of the product due to the creativity and imagination of the creator is significantly different from the traditional one. The creative economy can be seen as an economy in which economic agents create cultural, artistic, innovative goods and services. At the same time, they do not need production funds to create their products, they can create in urban, cultural spaces where they can showcase their work and exchange ideas. Creative economy is characterized by a creative approach, it is based on project thinking, creative imagination (modeling), practical direction.

The literature review

The term creative economy is called by different terms in different sources. For example, creative economy (Bloomberg, "Business week" magazine), cultural industry (T. Adorno and M. Horkheimer), creative industries (official document of the Great Britain Department of Culture, Media and Sports). The basic meaning of these concepts is to establish production based on creativity in the world economy. Furthermore John Newbigin, Special ex-Advisor to the Minister for Culture, Rt Hon Chris Smith MP, a member of the UK government's Creative

Industries Council; Chairman of the British Council's Advisory Group for Arts and Creative Economy; member of the Advisory Board of the Institute for Creative and Cultural Entrepreneurship at Goldsmiths, University of London; and of the Arts and Humanities Research Council's Knowledge Exchange Oversight Group did a massive research on this topic. Hasan Bakshi MBE, Director of Creative Industries Policy and Research at Nesta in London also studied measuring the creative industries and offered some methods. In addition to this Dr Tom Fleming, Tom Fleming Creative Consultancy found the leading role of The UK in supporting the creative economic policy.

Methods

In this article, historical and empirical methods were used to study the creative economy of Great Britain. In making proposals for Uzbekistan, methods of analogy, comparison and orientation from abstraction to precision were used.

The analysis and results

According to John Newbigin, an Honoured Professor at the University of Hong Kong, a member of the UK Government's Creative Industries Committee, the term "Creative Industries" began to be used around two decades ago to describe a range of activities, some of which are among the oldest in history, and some have emerged with the advent of digital technology. It should be recognized that the creative economy includes not only digital technologies, but also creative industries such as theater, dance, music, cinema, visual arts.

Cultural and creative industries (CCI) make up about three percent of the world's gross domestic product and employ almost 30 million of the world's population. The resolution of the United Nations declaring 2021 as the International Year of the Creative Economy for Sustainable Development confirms the growing role of this industry on a global scale.

Today, there are 3 major creative industry segments in the global market: Asia-Pacific (AP), Europe and North America segments. Globally, the AP segment is a haven for creative leaders with a high demand for consumer-oriented newspapers and video games. The book market in India is very developed and ranks 10th in the world in terms of income from book sales. Since 1990, the focus on the development of information and media technologies in Seoul has made it known today as a major cybersports exporter in the world [4].

The European market is based on historical heritage, art and fashion, and 7 of the 10 most visited museums in the world are also located in this region. 30 of the 69 creative cities in the world are located in Europe. While Britain is the leader in the arts market, the US and Canada are prominent in creative services and audiovisual media: TV, film production and radio. Here, 47% of the population is considered a consumer of cultural content. In Europe and Asia, this figure is 25% and 24%, respectively [1].

Although the creative industry has already begun to play a major role in the US economy, Great Britain has become one of the leading countries in the world that has begun to place special emphasis on this industry. In 1997, the newly elected Labor government in Great Britain decided to identify and assess their direct impact on the British economy. Based on Creative Nation - the study in 1994, including advice from an ad hoc group of leading creative entrepreneurs, published by the Australian government, the British government's new Department for Culture, Media and Sport published the Creative Industries Mapping Document in 1998. This document lists 13 key sectors of the creative industries. They are

advertising, architecture, art and antiques, craft, design, designer fashion, film, interactive entertainment software, music, performing arts, publishing, software, television and radio. Their common feature is that they stem from individual creativity, skill and talent. As well as they have the potential to create wealth through the registration of intellectual property. The concept of intellectual property (in other words, the value of an idea that can be protected by copyright, patents, trademarks, or other legal and regulatory mechanisms to stop the idea from being copied or commercialized without permission) has taken a central place in any explanation of the creative industries and is one of the concepts that continues to this day.¹

Below we look at the achievements of Uzbekistan and Great Britain in the components of the Global Innovation Index in a diagram resembling a cut onion.

Figure 1. The comparative graph of the global position of the countries of Uzbekistan and Great Britain according to the sectors of the Global Innovation Index²

As can be seen from this graph, the closer the points are to the center, the better the results of the countries. Great Britain is almost in the center and keeps its place in The First 10 according to the given indicators. Of course, it ranks 13th and 24th in the world according to the complexity of business and the activity of institutions. Although Uzbekistan tried to get closer to the center according to the indicators such as institutions, market sophistication, and infrastructure, anyway in many fields, it recorded 60-90th places in the world.

We ask, why is Britain in the 2nd place in the world in terms of production of creative products? The reason for this is that the UK's Department of Culture, Media and Sport (DCMS) has been very quick to digitize the results in the above 13 areas. That is, each country uses Standard Industrial Codes (SIC) and Standard Employment Codes (SEC) to compile its national accounts. The beginning of performing the results of creative industries according to these codes gave a clear picture of the change in their economic profile. However, these statistics have also caused some confusion. These are:

1. Indicators have sparked a never-ending debate between creativity and intellectual property as to why certain areas should or should not be included.

¹ <https://creativeeconomy.britishcouncil.org/guide/what-creative-economy/>

² <https://www.wipo.int/gii-ranking/en/compare?country1=uzbekistan&country2=united-kingdom>

2. The administration's reluctance to maintain a separate base for cultural spheres has caused the overlap of creative and cultural spheres.

3. It has become clear that there is no clear cut to classify which fields are creative and which are not. For example, it was said that accountants or technicians working in the creative field cannot be representatives of the creative field. On the other hand the staff responsible for design in the factory or companies had to be shown as representatives of the creative field.³

The main reasons for the development of these industries in Britain are:

- the rising Tax Reliefs,
- the wide geographical location
- and the presence of a constant potential consumer.

The representatives of creative industries also indicate the following as the main reason.

These are:

- Ability to react to an unexpected opportunity, such as a customer request or a potential crisis
- Pursue a “Burning Idea” or innovation and strive to make it a reality
- The desire to achieve high success in the creative field
- Maintaining competitiveness
- Personal aspirations, such as a certain lifestyle or the ability to work in a certain style or environment
- Always find motivation to engage in the profession you like
- Pursuit of stable income.⁴

Conclusion and offers

We know that production in the economy always depends on limited resources: land, capital, labor and raw materials. In the creative economy, the human factor can take advantage of unlimited resources, i.e., creativity and ability. This allows us to imagine the wide possibilities of this field. You can make a simple meal and benefit. A little creative approach to this business and having a Michelin star (A Michelin star gives restaurants, cafes and food stores special adoration from world-known critiquers and this makes other people taste their product at any cost) can achieve even more results.

Uzbekistan has long been a country of craftsmen. As a result of the attention to innovation and other cultural fields, the field of information technology is also developing rapidly. The British experience shows that if sufficient conditions are created for this sector, it is possible to increase its share in GDP. In addition, achieving the employment of the unemployed part of the population in the field also helps to increase economic well-being. Therefore, the support of the creative industry at the state level, the cooperation of government officials and representatives of civil society, and the creative population will make it possible to speed it up.

³ <https://creativeconomy.britishcouncil.org/guide/measuring-creative-industries/>

⁴ Creative industries: What creative enterprises need to thrive and grow. Creative Industries Federation, 2018.

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